

Investigation program for the reuse of an existing pile foundation system in Budapest

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ABSTRACT

Budapest has been changing in the last few decades. The industrial areas built around the old city center were demolished or converted. In place of these old factories, exclusive office buildings or residential buildings have been built.

The planning area was the site of a former printing press building constructed with deep foundations, the remaining existing foundation system of which is intended to be used as part of the foundation system of a new building complex. In almost half of the project area there are ~400 pcs of piles existing, about which there is no further information. By using a large number of old piles, foundation costs could be reduced by 30-45%. In addition to the economic benefits, there is also a technical interest in using the previous piles, since new piles cannot be designed without knowledge of the existing ones.

For using the old piles, special tests were carried out to determine the exact location of the piles, their diameter, length and concrete quality. In order to compare the load capacity of the piles with the load capacity that can be calculated from EC7 conform calculation formulae, 2 pile load tests were carried out.

PLANNED DEVELOPMENT

A new mixed-function residential building is planned to be built in Budapest, Hungary. The building will have 1 basement level and 5 to 9 floors above ground level. The expected contact pressures at the foundation level range from ~30 to 230 kPa, therefore a deep foundation system was considered for the design.

The plot was used as a railway distribution center at the end of the 19th century and a printing press building built in the 1970s and 1980s. The building was demolished in 2008. The foundation of the demolished press building was a reinforced concrete pile deep foundation system. Its remains can still be found on the site as the piles could not have been removed.

During the design process, the existing piles were seen as an opportunity, as these could be used as part of the foundation of the new building. Therefore, an extensive investigation program was carried out on the site with excavation, pile integrity and bearing capacity tests.

SITE HISTORY, EXISTING STRUCTURES

Detailed site history research was conducted to have an idea of the buried structures and geotechnical conditions. There are multiple options for site histories in Hungary, but in this case, most of the relevant information was available via open access web databases providing topographical maps and old photographs (Fig. 1-4.).

The site is located on a part of Budapest which was an industrial hub in the late 19th century, but later in the 1960s started to be developed as a mainly residential area. A printing press was built in 1967-1979 on the same parcel number, and the railway distribution center next to the site was demolished at

the end of the 1980s, providing more area for residential investments. There are several databases of very old (18th-19th century) topographical maps and architectural plans in Hungary, which are free to access (www.arcanum.hu). It is also possible to look up data in the archives. Old airplane photographs are available from the end of 1960s on www.fentrol.hu for free.

Past geotechnical reports and architectural plans can also be found in the Construction Documentation and Information Center of the Lechner Knowledge Center, where the original construction plans of the printing press were found. These plans were later used to determine the positions of the existing piles on the site. Pile groups of 2-6 bored piles were designed under each column of the building, and a piled raft foundation was used under the press machines. The diameter of the buried piles are 0.52m and 0.83m, their lengths are 7.5 m and 13.5m with bases at 94.50 m a.B.s.l. and 88.50 m a.B.s.l. (a.B.s.l.=above Baltic sea level).

Figure 1 – Railway hub in the 1960s (<https://villamosok.hu/balazs/bpvasut/ipvg/viza/index.html>)

Figure 2. – Printing Press Building in the 1980s (<https://hu.museum-digital.org/singleimage.php?imagenr=398029>)

Figure 3. – Old railway station next to the site in 2008
(<http://www.vasutallomasok.hu/allomas.php?az=bviz>)

Figure 4. – Airplane photograph of the site with the printing press from 1996 (www.fentrol.hu)

The geotechnical conditions can be summarized as the following: 1.3-3.6m thick man-made, heterogenous fill covers the surface containing a large amount of debris, crushed brick, concrete and gravel. Underlying the fill, a silty, clayey sand layer with high organic content was explored, on the eastern part of the site, down to a depth of -2.8-6.2m. On western parts of the plot, where the organic layer was not present, a silty sand, sandy silt layer was found to a depth of -5.7-7.4m. Under these layers, the coarse-grained sediment of the Danube river (sandy gravel, gravelly sand) was explored to a depth of -8.8-10.5m. The bedrock in the geotechnical model is an Oligocene/Miocene clay with hard and very hard consistencies providing a competent layer for foundation structures.

EXPLORATION OF THE PILE POSITIONS

The printing press building has two foundation plans available in the Documentation center, one from 1975 and the other from 1977. At the start of the investigations, only the plan dated to 1975 was available. At first, 12 pile groups were selected for excavation to measure the positions and diameters of the piles and conduct low strain dynamic integrity tests on them. The excavated positions did not match well with the expected spacings according to the available plans, therefore a second round of literature search turned up the plans dated to 1977, which matched the explored pile positions much better. A change in some of the pile positions – possibly due to changes in the design or load distribution – was apparent, but these plans nearly exactly matched the explored positions, the deviation from the 1977 plans was on average 20-30 cm. Finally, we excavated the top of 34 piles of the 387 piles.

The diameter of the excavated piles was generally 5-10cm larger than designed, there was only 1 out of the 34 piles that had a 77cm diameter instead of 83cm. The difference in diameters most likely comes from the bored cased piling technology that was used for the construction.

Figure 5. – Some of the excavated top of the piles

DETERMINATION OF THE CONCRETE STRENGTH AND YOUNG'S MODULUS

Schmidt-hammer tests were carried out to estimate the concrete strength and the Young's modulus of the piles. The results of the tests indicated, that the concrete strength of the piles varies between 32.3-48.91 MPa, with an average of 43.10MPa and a standard deviation of 6.33 MPa, therefore it conforms to a C30/37 concrete strength according to MSZ EN 4798:2016+A1:2018. The original plans mention the cement type as S54 350 PC, which can be used for sulphate-resistant concrete, and conforms to a CEM I 32,5 S cement type according to the current classification. Based on the measurements, the concrete quality was found to be in compliance with the environmental class XA1 (MSZ EN 206:2013+2:2021) as determined by the groundwater and soil chemistry analyses performed in the Ground Investigation Report.

DETERMINATION OF THE PILE LENGTHS

The length of the piles was estimated from a low strain dynamic integrity test. To carry out the test in advance, concrete samples were taken from 6 of the excavated piles for the laboratory to determine the unit density of the concrete used. The results of the test varied between 2.24-2.35 t/m³. These results, and the approximated Young's modulus from Schmidt-hammer tests, were used to estimate the P-wave velocity of the concrete material as 3858 m/s with a standard deviation of 88m/s. Comparing these velocities with the wave travel time from integrity tests, the length and base level of the excavated piles was estimated. Minimum and maximum pile lengths resulting from the mean $\pm 2\sigma$ modulus range (95% probability) with calculated propagation velocities. Minimum lengths are shown by the light green bars and maximum lengths by the dark green bars in Figure 6. Based on these, the minimum and maximum depths of the base of the pile were calculated and demonstrated in the Figure 7.

Figure 6. – Estimated max. and min. pile lengths (95% reliability)

Figure 7. – Estimated pile base levels and the 95% reliability interval; mathematical average base level marked with blue line

Based on the tests, 7 out of the 34 surveyed piles were found with a base level 0.1-0.4m higher than prescribed by the old design drawings. Presumably these shorter piles reached a harder, stiffer layer earlier, in which drilling slowed down, and therefore it may have been decided to assess the pile load capacity as adequate even with the shorter length. Another 13 piles were definitely over-drilled compared to the design, which may indicate that the harder, stiffer layer is only present at a larger depth than designed.

Based on the ground investigation report drillings, all tested piles were embedded in the clay layer. However, in the ground investigation drilling, the varied clay surface formed based on the length of the piles could not be seen, but a requirement in the plans that a sample of the hard clay at the base must be taken at each group of piles indicates that the construction was carried out carefully, so that the base of the piles rests reliably on the hard clay.

BEARING CAPACITY TESTS

In order to examine the original piling technology, the construction work at that time, the geometric accuracy of the completed piles, the properties of the soil layers and the effect of the behavior of the

piles on the pile bearing capacity, 2 buried piles were selected for bearing capacity tests. The selection was based on the location of the piles on site, so that one of them was on the eastern side with a thicker explored organic layer (12E), the other on the western side, where this layer is present with a smaller thickness and bigger depth.

The bearing capacity tests were made with 4 anchor piles, 80cm diameter each, and 10m depth, while the loaded piles had a diameter of 87 and 92 cm and a length of 11.6-12.2m. As the tops of the buried test piles were ~2-3m below ground level, extensions of the piles were necessary by concreting in a steel formwork (Fig. 8, 9). The main characteristics of the loaded pile are summarized in Tables 1 & 2.

Table 1. – Tested pile characteristics

Designation	Base level	Diameter	Calculated bearing capacity	Displacement at bearing capacity
	<i>[m aBsl]</i>	<i>[cm]</i>	<i>[kN]</i>	<i>[mm]</i>
6D	88,4	92,0	4 060	92
12E	88,6	87,0	3 360	87

Table 2. – Load steps

Load steps [kN]									
6D	500	1000	1500	2000	2500	3000	3550	4060	additional: 4450 kN
12E	420	840	1260	1680	2100	2520	2940	3360	additional: 3700 kN

Figure 8. – Installation of the formwork to extend the buried pile selected for load test

Figure 9. – Bearing capacity test with anchor piles

Each pile was tested in 8 load steps with consolidation in between each step. The piles were unloaded and reloaded after the second and fourth load step. Up to the first unloading, the consolidation was rapid for both piles, with settlements in the order of ~1mm. After the reloading phase, up to the fourth load step (1680kN; 2000kN), consolidation times increase significantly up to 1.5 hours per load step, but the post-consolidation settlements remain low, on the order of ~3mm. For subsequent load steps, the consolidation time was 2.5-3 hours, although during the loading of pile 12E, it was limited to 2 hours due to time constraints.

The measured load-settlement diagrams are shown on Figures 10 and 11. Settlements for the final load step of pile 6D were 32.5mm, while for 12E the measured vertical displacement was 28mm. Due to the low settlements, an additional load step of 4450kN and 3700kN was applied for both piles. In the case of pile 6D, the pile was in constant motion at this load with no sign of slowing down, therefore it was considered that the bearing capacity has been reached. Pile 12E was loaded 3697 kN with 42mm settlement, but the consolidation settlements decreased very slowly, showing that the applied load was near the bearing capacity of the pile.

Figure 10 (left)-11(right). – Force-settlement curve of the pile tests

Based on the load test results, an additional 10% bearing capacity was measured for each pile compared to the calculated value. The calculations are based on the Szepesházi-formula (2011), which is an EC7-based calculation corrected for Hungarian soils and piling company technology. The pile bearing capacities were measured as 4450 kN for pile 6D, and extrapolated based on load-settlement analyses and bearing capacity calculation as 4000kN for pile 12E. Based on the load-settlement curves, the values of the load-carrying components (shaft and base resistance) can be separated using graphical or analytical methods. The piles behave significantly stiffer until the skin resistance is exhausted than in the subsequent stage, during the mobilization of the base resistance. This stiffer behavior is reflected in the load-deflection curve as a lower slope, which is ~2200 kN for the 6D test load and ~1950 kN for the 12E test load. The mobilization of the base resistance is characterized by a larger slope, with a base resistance value of ~2250kN for test load 6D and ~2050kN for pile 12E. Based on the measured results, the displacement associated with the shaft resistance depletion is approximately ~1-1.5% of the pile diameter, which is slightly lower than the literature recommendations (Szepesházi, 2011) for drilled piles (2-3% of the diameter).

Table 3. – Load test results

Designation	Base resistance [kN]	Unit base resistance [MPa]	Shaft resistance [kN]	Unit shaft resistance [kPa]	Bearing capacity [kN]
6D	2250	3,38	2200	65,5	4450
12E	2050	3,45	1950	61,5	4000

The resistances determined from the evaluation of the load test results for the shaft resistance are almost the same as the shaft resistances calculated from the results of the CPTu tests in the field, the increase in the load capacity observed being due to the higher base resistance. Based on the assumed base resistances, the specific base resistance is estimated to be between 3.38MPa and 3.45MPa. Based on the test load results, the upper limit of the unit base resistance was proposed to be 3.30MPa, which is in good agreement with the results of other load tests made in Budapest.

SUMMARY

Based on the results of the pioneer investigation program in Hungary, it was determined that the existing piles do not follow the spacing of the load bearing structures of the planned development. Therefore, it would be very difficult and not cost-efficient to design a completely new piled raft foundation system without the use of the existing piles on the site, as the existing piles heavily limit the free space available for new piles. Instead of a piled raft, a rigid inclusion foundation system was considered as the most cost-efficient option without the complete redesign of the building to conform to the existing pile layouts. Detailed cost and carbon footprint analysis of the foundation system can be found in the conference paper titled “Using the piles of a building demolished decades before as the foundation of a modern building”.

The pile investigation and load test gave convincing evidence about the quality of the piles and their bearing capacity to be able to consider them as part of the new foundation system on about 60% of the layout. Aside from the cost-savings on the site, the elimination of a large amount of piles can also have wider economic impact, as it reduces the demand for new materials and reduces the impact of construction on the environment.

The project is under design now. At conceptual stage two potential solutions were prepared by the authors and further detailed in a separate paper presenting geotechnical design and carbon footprint analysis, as well.

REFERENCES

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